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ACCSESS Project: Providing access to cost-efficient, replicable, safe and flexible CCUS

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Abstract

ACCSESS project is a four-year Horizon 2020 Innovation Action that started in May 2021. The project vision is to "Develop replicable carbon capture, utilization, and storage (CCUS) pathways towards a Climate Neutral Europe in 2050. This paper shows a project overview. The project has a cross-sectorial approach addressing emissions from Pulp and Paper, Cement, Waste-to-Energy, and Biorefineries, all with potential for contributing to carbon dioxide removal (CDR). The ACCSESS concept redefines the CCS acronym as "Capture, Chains and Society", to address the fact that technical aspects, chain optimization and societal perspectives need to be considered together to accelerate CCS implementation in Europe. ACCSESS will demonstrate several innovative technology prototypes in an operational environment. This includes the pilot-scale demonstration of CO₂ capture technology at three industrial sites in three different countries. The capture technology innovation to be demonstrated is a solvent consisting of potassium carbonate dissolved in water, in combination with a Rotary Packed Bed (RPB) absorber. In addition, ACCSESS will explore energy- and cost-efficient ways to integrate CO₂ capture solvent technologies in the four industrial sectors and industry clusters. ACCSESS will develop and improve CCUS chains from continental Europe and the Baltic area to the North Sea, to provide access routes to the flexible, ship-based offshore CO₂ transport and storage infrastructures that are under development in the North Sea. The work will include multi-criteria optimization and assessments (techno-economic, environmental, legal/regulatory), to assess the holistic performance and overall feasibility of the chains and clusters. The selected CCUS chains are based on technological solutions for CO₂ capture and transport that are available today, and chains that rely on technologies that are still under development. Enabling technologies for CO₂ transport will be explored to ensure a multi-scale approach to de-risking CCUS chains. A main hypothesis in ACCSESS is that cities striving for sustainable urban development can become drivers for CCS implementation, which could lead to multiple replications of CCS in Europe. ACCSESS will engage with and inform stakeholders about CCS, its benefits for society, and the marginal additional cost of products produced with CCS. ACCSESS brings together researchers and CCS stakeholders from several pan-European countries in a joint effort to innovate and accelerate CCS deployment.

Keywords: CO₂ capture demonstration; CCS; CDR; CCUS Chains; Solvents; Technoeconomic Assessment; LCA; Legal and Regulatory; Society; Cities; Pulp and Paper; Cement; Waste-to-Energy; Biorefineries; Industrial Clusters.

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1. Introduction

In 2018, the IPCC Special Report on Global Warming of 1.5 °C clearly showed that climate neutrality will require drastic emission cuts as well as net Carbon Dioxide Removal (CDR) from the atmosphere [1]. The EU Green Deal proposes to deliver drastic emission cuts – with a 55% cut to 2030 and net zero by 2050 compared to 1990 levels. Deep greenhouse gas emission reductions from the industry will be required to achieve this target, and net GHG removal from the atmosphere will be needed at large scale to compensate for sectors where complete decarbonization is challenging. CDR technologies, including CCUS, need to be deployed at scale to meet this demand.

Strengthened climate goals and new investment incentives have resulted in an unprecedented momentum for CCS across the world. As per 2021, CCUS facilities around the world have the capacity to capture more than 40 MtCO₂ a year [2]. Plans for more than 100 new facilities were announced in 2021 [3]. It is becoming more and more evident that CCS technologies will play an important role in meeting net-zero CO₂ targets, and many net-zero plans list CCS as a necessity, not an option. However, this is far from sufficient, and work is still needed if we are to deploy CCS technologies at the scale needed and achieve a net-zero Europe by 2050 [3]. If we are to make CCS a relevant, large-scale technology for cutting carbon dioxide (CO₂) emissions, several barriers need to be addressed, and its deployment must be accelerated.

The ACCSESS project is a four-year Horizon 2020 Innovation Action that started in May 2021. The project vision is to "Develop replicable carbon capture, utilization, and storage (CCUS) pathways towards a Climate Neutral Europe in 2050 [4]". ACCSESS has in particular been conceived to respond to the need for carbon dioxide removal (CDR), and address current barriers to large-scale CCS deployment. The project aims to accelerate innovations and will demonstrate CO₂ capture (non-amine solvent) and CO₂ use (mineralization) at a Technology Readiness Level (TRL) of 7 (system prototype demonstration in operational environment).

ACCSESS takes a cross-sectorial approach to CCUS, working with industries from the Pulp and Paper, Cement, Waste to Energy and Biorefining sectors. These sectors all have a potential to realise CDR, but to a varying degree, due to different industrial constraints. Gathering several industrial sectors in one project enables fostering cross sectorial learning within the field of CCUS.

This paper introduces the ACCSESS project concept and how the project re-invents the CCS acronym, how the project addresses drastic CO₂ emissions cuts and CDR potential in four key industries, its highlighted innovations, and includes a description of the plans for CO₂ capture pilot of an enzymatic solvent with a rotary packed bed absorber in different industries and locations in Europe. To conclude, the ACCSESS consortium is presented.

Nomenclature

BECCS	Bioenergy Carbon Capture and Storage
CCS	Carbon Capture and Storage
CCUS	Carbon Capture, Utilization, and Storage
CDR	Carbon Dioxide Removal
GHG	Greenhouse Gas
IPCC	Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change
TRL	Technology Readiness Level
WtE	Waste-to-Energy

2. ACCSESS concept: Capture, Chains and Society

In the context of fighting climate change, the acronym "CCS" traditionally refers to CO₂ Capture and Storage. In ACCSESS CCS is also redefined as "Capture, Chains and Society". This means that, in addition to covering technical challenges of CCS, the project zooms out and takes a societal perspective on the key challenges that need to be addressed for CCS to be successfully implemented across Europe and globally. This project concept is illustrated in Fig. 1. As can be seen, the concept is centered around its vision to develop replicable CCUS pathways towards a climate-neutral Europe in 2050.

Figure 1. ACCESS concept with its vision at the centre: Replicable CCS pathways towards a climate neutral Europe in 2050.

2.1. Capture

2.1.1 CO₂ capture for CDR

ACCESS will explore energy- and cost-efficient ways to integrate capture technologies in industrial installations as a key element to accelerate CCUS implementation. As a project dedicated to CDR, focus is on the four industry segments that emit partly or fully biogenic CO₂. Efficient heat integration can enable significant reduction of the cost and energy requirement for the capture step of the CCS chain. This is particularly relevant for capture integration in industrial processes. ACCESS partners will perform systematic process integration studies of CO₂ capture for pulp and paper, cement, waste to energy and biorefineries, with the objective to cut CO₂ avoidance costs by 20-30% with respect to end-of-pipe CO₂ capture with the benchmark solvent, consisting of blends of two amines: amino-methylpropanol (AMP) and piperazine (PZ) [5]. The AMP-PZ solvent was suggested recently as new benchmark based on studies from the CESAR project [6].

ACCESS will demonstrate innovative CO₂ capture technology prototypes in an operational environment (TRL7). The project includes two highlighted innovations related to CO₂ capture:

- **Innovation 1:** ACCESS will demonstrate at TRL7, on a ca. 2 tons per day scale, post-combustion CO₂ capture with a non-amine, non-toxic enzyme enhanced solvent, the CO₂ solutions by SAIPEM technology [7]. This opens opportunities for employing low-temperature industrial waste heat for CO₂ capture purposes. The enzyme enhanced solvent is combined with a novel and compact rotary packed bed (RPB) absorber. CO₂ avoidance cost cuts are expected both due to the low regeneration temperature and the compact RPB absorber. CO₂ capture testing will focus on three industrial sectors (pulp and paper, waste to energy and cement). See section 4 for more details.
- **Innovation 2:** The lack of steam or low-temperature waste heat on many cement kiln sites calls for radically new thinking for minimizing CO₂ capture cost and energy penalties. The innovation will be the development of a radically new cement kiln integrated with amine capture, designed for operation with biomass as fuel. The kiln will combine structural elements (e.g., for preheater tower and CO₂ absorber) and operational synergies will be identified.

2.1.2 CO₂ use for CDR

Although largely focusing on CCS, the project includes a highlighted technology innovation related to use of captured CO₂ with permanent removal from the atmosphere (i.e. enabling CDR) related to the cement sector. This technology will be demonstrated in operational environment (TRL7):

- **Innovation 3:** CO₂ use will be demonstrated at TRL7 with an innovative, continuous two-step process for mineral carbonation of demolition concrete [8]. The resulting product can be used as a filling material in novel concrete, hence reducing the use of sand and gravel [9]. This solution not only enables permanent storage of CO₂ in novel constructions, but provided that the CO₂ originates from biogenic sources, it also provides an option for CDR on a smaller scale than geological storage. Outside ACCSESS, the technology is currently being developed at TRL5 (technology validated in relevant environment) and will be brought further to TRL7 in ACCSESS.

2.2. Chains

The roll out and implementation of CCUS chains is challenging. Complex strategies will be required for the cost-efficient deployment of a European CCS infrastructure, including capture deployment timelines, technological transport options, CO₂ sink availability, spatial and time deployment constraints, and the cost specificity of each CCS chain item. The successful roll out of CCS chains at the required time and scale will require holistic approaches across sectors and national borders, and that involve several stakeholders [10].

ACCSESS will develop and improve CCUS chains from continental Europe and the Baltic area to the North Sea, to provide access routes to the flexible, ship-based offshore CO₂ transport and storage infrastructures that are under development in the North Sea. The work in ACCSESS will include multi-criteria optimization and assessments, to assess the holistic performance and overall feasibility of the chains:

- **Techno-economic optimization:** The work will include the development, design, and techno-economic evaluation of several CCS chains, both chains that are based on technological solutions for CO₂ capture and transport that are available today [11], and chains rely on technologies that are still under development.
- **Legal/regulatory aspects:** ACCSESS will address the regulatory frameworks, gaps, and environmental performance of CCS chains [11]. An open-source CO₂ network optimization model that considers how CCS networks can evolve over space and time will also be developed.
- **Environmental performance:** The overall emissions connected to the carbon capture, transport, and storage chain will be quantified with life cycle assessment (LCA) [12].

Clustering of industrial CO₂ emissions as well as development of shared transport infrastructure can be key elements to reduce cost and enable realization of CCUS in European industry. By optimizing CCUS chains and completing comprehensive studies that cover business models, legal/regulatory and environmental aspects, ACCSESS will provide the tools and expertise needed to reduce or remove barriers to decision-makers across CCUS chains as well as society at large.

In addition, enabling technologies for CO₂ transport will be explored to ensure a multi-scale approach to de-risking CCUS chains. Research will be conducted on technological solutions for enabling low-cost CO₂ transport, such as increasing the understanding of the kinetics of dry ice formation and melting when handling CO₂ along the transport chain, defining safe loading and off-loading procedures for CO₂ transport on ships, and addressing aspects of water content design specifications for CO₂ transport.

2.3. Society

For CCS to successfully contribute to significantly curbing CO₂ emissions, it needs to become an integrated and obvious part of the society and its infrastructure. In this context, a main hypothesis in ACCSESS is that cities striving for sustainable urban development can become drivers for CCS implementation, which could lead to multiple replications of CCS across Europe. ACCSESS will therefore engage with and inform stakeholders about CCS, its

benefits for society, and the marginal additional cost of products produced with CCS [13]. ACCSESS therefor aims to explain CCS and CCUS, to create an understanding and acceptance among cities and citizens of the solutions that CCS can contribute, and therewith contribute to the development of the future low-carbon society that is needed for combatting global warming. More concretely, ACCSESS will synthesize consortium competence and project results in a concrete and understandable manner in brief reports that explain the "what" and "how" of CCS from a city perspective.

Concepts of CCS end products supply and value chains were developed in earlier work on cement, steel, and pulp and paper [13]. ACCSESS will further show how CCS and CDR can substantially reduce the carbon footprint of end products, with only a marginal increase in cost [14]. ACCSESS will work with potential opportunities to make carbon negativity a valued aspect of a product. Increasing the demand for low-carbon and even carbon-negative products could, by extension, increase the demand for CCS. This includes that cities and governments could use public procurement of low-carbon materials to achieve their climate ambitions at a reasonable cost. ACCSESS will also engage with environmental authorities in Germany and Sweden to further develop guidelines for how to regulate CO₂ capture installations.

3. Addressing drastic CO₂ emissions cuts and CDR in four key industries

Carbon dioxide removal (CDR) generally describes ways to remove greenhouse gases (GHG) from the atmosphere. One way of doing this is through the capture of biogenic CO₂ emissions to be permanently and safely stored. This method is often called "bioenergy with carbon capture and storage" (BECCS). "Biogenic CO₂ emissions" refers to CO₂ emissions that have been produced by burning plant-based material, also known as biomass. When biomass is burned, it releases the CO₂ that the plant absorbed during its lifetime through photosynthesis. In principle, if biogenic CO₂ emissions are captured and permanently removed from the atmosphere, we will have achieved "carbon-negative" emissions (in other words, a certain process will have removed more CO₂ from the atmosphere than it released). In order to claim that carbon dioxide removals are achieved, it is essential that the CO₂ is stored in a manner intended to be permanent and that the GHG emissions associated with the removal and storage processes are included in the estimation, including the biomass origin, energy use and gas fate [15].

3.1. Focus on four industrial sectors

The extent to which CCS is effective can vary depending on the characteristics of each industrial sector, specific site conditions, etc. ACCSESS comprises partners from four industrial sectors in Europe with the potential to implement CDR: pulp and paper, cement, waste-to-energy, and biorefineries.

- **Pulp and paper:** In the Nordic countries, a kraft pulp mill mainly relies on biomass for its energy supply, and therefore a large share of the CO₂ emissions captured from this sector are biogenic (approx. 75-100%, depending on the energy supply). Therefore, the permanent geological storage of these emissions could significantly contribute to CDR [16].
- **Waste-to-energy (WtE):** The type of fuel in the WtE sector will naturally vary but can typically be around 50% biogenic, and therefore, the captured CO₂ emissions from this sector can be estimated to be around 50% biogenic. Currently, around 500 WtE plants in Europe play an important role in waste management and often also in energy supply. WtE with CCS could add an additional role for WtE plants as carbon-negative emissions providers, making them a potential contributor to CDR [17].
- **Cement:** When burning biofuels or waste-derived fuels in a cement kiln, only up to ~1/3 of the CO₂ in the flue gases can be biogenic, since roughly 2/3 of the CO₂ emitted from cement production comes from the calcination of limestone. In other words, depending on the provenance of the fuel, up to 30% of the captured CO₂ can theoretically contribute to CDR. From an industrial plant perspective, the actual potential for CDR from cement industry might be significantly lower because 100% biogenic fuel is probably difficult and 90% capture rate expensive. Considering the global perspective, the cement sector is responsible for 6-7% of all global, man-made

CO₂ emissions [18], meaning that a small portion of biogenic CO₂ captured from several cement kilns could make a certain contribution to CDR.

- **Biorefineries:** In addition to biofuel, biorefineries typically also produce CO₂ and other by-products. The CO₂ produced from processing biomass is normally vented to atmosphere. However, if it were captured and securely stored in geological formations, the produced biofuel could be characterized by net negative emissions due to the biogenic nature of the CO₂ [19]. Typically, Captured CO₂ could be up to 50% biogenic in retrofitted biorefineries, and up to 100% in green-field biorefineries.

Figure 2. The ability of the industrial sectors covered by ACCSESS to contribute to CDR, assuming a 90% CO₂ capture rate.

As shown in Fig.2, these four sectors have the potential to not only drastically cut their own emissions and contribute to CDR, but also contribute to reducing Europe's CO₂ emissions, provided that the financial, legal and regulatory contexts are in place. The CO₂ captured from the industrial installations in these sectors must generally be stored underground, but minor CO₂ streams can be used to create other products. While the challenges and opportunities for CCS deployment in the four different sectors are largely industry specific, ACCSESS aims to boost cross-sectional learnings among its partners on CCS aspects related to CO₂ capture and its integration, roll out of CCS chains in the pan-European zone and societal integration of CCS.

3.2. Chemical absorption with solvents to capture CO₂

A range of CO₂ capture technologies are currently available, each at different technological maturity levels. One of them, arguably the most mature one, is "post-combustion CO₂ capture based on liquid chemical solvents" (absorption), which refers to the use of liquid solvents to capture CO₂ from flue gases. Several types of solvent technologies or chemical solvents can be used in absorption, with different performance characteristics, quantities and quality of energy required for capturing the CO₂. ACCSESS will address systematic and innovative ways of integrating solvents, in four industrial sectors that each use varying amounts of biomass in their fuel or feedstock.

4. CO₂ capture piloting

4.1. Testing an environmentally friendly solvent

A main activity in the ACCSESS project is pilot-scale demonstration of CO₂ capture technology at three industrial sites in three different countries, all with a flue gas that partly or fully comes from burning biomass. The capture

technology to be demonstrated is a solvent consisting of potassium carbonate dissolved in water, in combination with a Rotary Packed Bed (RPB) absorber. Carbonic anhydrase, which is the same enzyme that aids CO₂ transport in our lungs, is added to act as catalyst for a quicker CO₂ uptake and release [7]. This technology is provided by CO₂ solutions by Saipem. The demonstration route for the CO₂ solutions by Saipem technology with the Prospin/Proceler RPB absorber is shown in Fig. 3.

4.2. Test campaigns of CO₂ solutions by Saipem solvent and RPB

Figure 3. The demonstration route for the CO₂ solutions by Saipem technology with the Prospin/Proceler RPB absorber.

- **Rig commissioning and testing at Waste to Energy plant:** The enzymatic technology is tested for the first time in Europe at Fortum Oslo Varme (now Hafslund Oslo Celsio) in Norway, at the Klemetsrud waste-to-energy plant. A full-scale CO₂ capture project using another technology has already been developed for the Klemetsrud plant [20], but its owners continue to support the realisation of CCS. This includes allowing their mobile CO₂ capture test rig to be used in the ACCSESS project. The pilot rig is shown in Fig. 4.
- **Testing at Technology Center Mongstad (TCM):** Following the Klemetsrud tests, the mobile test rig will be transported to TCM in Norway, where a novel piece of equipment will be added in its own separate container: a rotary packed bed (RPB) absorber. The RPB absorber is constructed by the ACCSESS partner Prospin and its linked third party Proceler. The RPB absorber has the potential to further improve CO₂ capture by generating centrifugal forces that will enable the enzymatic solvent to absorb CO₂ even more quickly. The RPB absorber is transported to TCM in autumn 2022 from Łódź in Poland. At TCM, tests will run with both the conventional absorber and the RPB absorber in order to achieve the best possible comparison between these two types of technology.
- **Test campaign at kraft pulp mill:** After a few months at TCM, the mobile capture test rig, including the RPB will be transported to the Stora Enso kraft pulp mill in Skutskär, Sweden, for a long-term test campaign. The mill produces fluff, for e.g. diapers, from forest residuals such as treetops and branches. The biomass waste from the fluff production is burned as an integrated part of the production process, resulting in 1.2 Mtonnes of CO₂ emission

per year that are 100% from biomass, meaning that there is a very interesting potential for CDR here. A test run of around several months will provide valuable insights into how Saipem's solvent combined with the Prospin/Proceler RPB absorber performs on this type of flue gas.

- **Test campaign at cement kiln:** Finally, from Skutskär, the pilot test rig will be transported to its final ACCSESS stop: the HeidelbergCement's cement kiln in Góraźdźe, Poland – not very far from where the RPB absorber is developed and produced. This is one of Europe's largest cement kilns, with CO₂ emissions of 2.5 Mtonnes/year. When burning solid residual fuels (SRF), there will typically be a share of biogenic CO₂ in the exhaust, but how much will depend on the fuel. As explained in section 3.1, there is a potential for CDR from cement kilns, like the one in Góraźdźe.

Figure 4. The Hafslund Oslo Celsio CO₂ capture pilot rig, adapted for operation with the CO₂ solutions by Saipem technology.

5. Accelerating innovation

The ACCSESS consortium includes partners from major European industry sectors that are relevant to the successful implementation of CCS. The cross-border and interdisciplinary nature of ACCSESS' work, as well as the consideration of cities as key drivers for sustainability, will lay the foundations for activating the required regional and international cooperation needed to ensure a clean and secure energy transition at affordable prices.

ACCSESS brings together researchers and CCS stakeholders from several European countries in a joint effort to accelerate CCS deployment [4]. By addressing CCS innovation related to "CO₂ capture, chains and society", as well as investigating drastic CO₂ emissions cuts and removal in four key industries, ACCSESS will contribute to the

increasing momentum towards the deployment of CCS technology in Europe and provide replicable CCS pathways to achieve a climate-neutral Europe by 2050.

Figure 5. ACCSESS focuses on CCS through smart interactions between policy, academia, industry and citizens.

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